

Spectral filter design based on in-field hyperspectral imaging and machine learning for mango ripeness estimation

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Abstract

Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) is a powerful technology already used for many objectives in agriculture. Applications include disease monitoring, plant phenotyping, yield estimation or fruit composition and ripeness. However, the cost of hyperspectral sensors is typically an order of magnitude higher than simpler RGB cameras, which can be prohibitive. Given that in HSI processing the spectral data often contains redundancies, the full spectra are not always required for a specific application and there is an opportunity to design a lower cost multi-spectral sensing system by dimensionality reduction. In past work, HSI dimensionality reduction has been applied in the form of band selection to achieve faster computation times. If, however, the objective is to design a lower cost multi-spectral camera system, band selection is poorly suited because real-world sensor and optical filter responses do not typically replicate the individual bands of a hyperspectral sensor. The objective of this paper is to develop a new methodology for filter selection by simulating several imaging devices with different real-world optical filters, to use a high cost HSI device to design a lower cost multi-spectral solution for a specific application. In this paper, we apply the technique to the specific task of mango fruit maturity estimation (dry matter), which was recently shown to be possible using HSI. Mango HSI acquired under field conditions from an UGV was used as input for the experiments. These involved the simulation of imaging devices, using support vector machines for modelling, and testing several filter combinations by brute force or optimisation with genetic algorithms. The mango prediction performance of the simulations was compared to the best performance obtained with full HSI data, which had an R^2 of 0.74. The best values came from the simulation of a four-sensor device with four distinct filters, achieving R^2 up to 0.69 for mango dry matter estimation. The results showed that genetic algorithms, when compared to brute force approaches, were able to obtain the best solution in an efficient way, and that a good performance for mango ripeness estimation can be achieved from the combination of four spectral filters that would allow to implement them into a low-cost, custom-made multi-spectral sensor. The methods exposed in this paper are more broadly applicable to applications beyond mango maturity estimation.

Keywords: filter selection, band selection, genetic algorithms, optimisation, field robotics, computer vision, hyperspectral, spectroscopy, dry matter

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1. Introduction

Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) is actively studied for many food and agricultural applications [31, 38]. HSI combines high spatial resolution imaging such as commonly done using simpler RGB cameras, with high spectral resolution more commonly used in spectroscopy. Because many physical properties can be derived from the analysis of the interaction between light and matter [36], HSI is useful for estimating traits or characteristics of visible objects. In the context of precision agriculture, recent studies have shown HSI applications for plant disease monitoring [41, 26, 29], phenotyping [3, 28, 20, 11] or fruit composition [6, 35, 43, 19], which have all been developed in laboratory and not field conditions. By contrast, publications describing in-field HSI applications are less common, but efforts in this area have been increasing recently. HSI has been manually acquired under field conditions for the segmentation of raspberry plants [49], and also mounted on phenotyping platforms [5]. Terrestrial vehicles for on-the-go HSI acquisition were also employed for varietal classification in grapevines [15] (manned platform), mango ripeness prediction [48] or yield estimation [16] at whole-orchard scale (unmanned platforms). Detailed studies also exist describing the technical details for using hyperspectral sensing on unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) concerning illumination compensation [47] or extrinsic parameter calibration [46]. In agricultural applications, the high-resolution data gathering from HSI in both spectral (hundreds of channels) and spatial dimensions (especially when acquired at close range from ground vehicles) make this technology suitable for detailed in-field monitoring of crops. Nevertheless, hyperspectral cameras are typically more expensive than other sensing technologies. Additionally, it is known that spectral data—generally represented as vectors with several hundreds of variables (bands or channels)—suffers from high information redundancy, especially between adjacent bands [52]. Consequently, given the high cost and redundancy of HSI, the question arises, is it really necessary to use all the bands from spectral data, acquired at significant cost, or is it possible to obtain virtually the same information after dimensionality reduction? Simplification of the input could lead to options for lower cost sensor systems that are designed to match specific applications.

Spectral dimensionality reduction (from any kind of sources, not only limited to HSI) is a costly procedure due to its combinatorial complexity [50], especially if an exhaustive search is performed. For this reason, different machine learning metaheuristics are commonly used to optimise the selection of spectral bands. Some of these techniques include genetic algorithms (GAs) [30, 24, 32], particle swarm optimization [50, 53, 4] or ant colony optimisation [39, 13, 42]. Nevertheless, while most of the studies seek to provide a reduced selection of spectral bands, they lack one important factor: the channels they propose, regardless of their number, are individual and based on the original spectrum. If the acquisition of those specific channels is attempted to check its reproducibility, the only feasible way would be to use a spectral sensor capable of acquiring full high-resolution spectra that covers the selected wavelengths, and then isolate those specific individual datapoints. For example, nine and twelve different wavelengths for two datasets were selected in [23], while up to dozens of wavelengths were reported in [12] for endmember extraction in hyperspectral images. Specifically, in agricultural applications, in [30] the authors used GAs for band selection on soybean disease detection from HSI, reporting that six specific wavelengths maximised the performance for the desired task. A methodology for grapevine water status estimation based on [near-infrared spectroscopy \(NIR\)](#) was reported in [14], and, from [Visible-NIR spectroscopy](#), selected five specific bands within a very narrow range

40 between 700 and 800 nm that highly correlated with water content. For the same grapevine water status
41 prediction goal, an older study [54] also reported good results when reducing the number of variables to 25
42 from full Vis-NIR spectra. While the results from these studies met their objective to reduce computational
43 complexity in data processing, the same process cannot be readily applied to developing low-cost ad-hoc
44 spectral sensors, particularly when dozens of bands have been selected.

45 Assuming that it is desired to build a multi-band spectral sensor after identifying a reduced set of
46 narrow-band wavelengths using any of the methodologies described before, it would be very difficult to
47 obtain measurements of those bands in any other way than using HSI and discarding the surplus data. This
48 is due to manufacturing limitations in optical filter design and also because of the poor light signal-to-noise
49 ratio (SNR) that is obtained when very narrow filters are employed. Several works on different methodologies
50 for filter design have also reported these difficulties [21, 17, 18, 45]. In [34] and [51], the authors attempted
51 the simulation of colour filters by optimising three, five and 10 filters in terms of amplitude, efficiency and/or
52 SNR. Special attention should be paid to two papers on the practical implications of the development of
53 cameras based on multi-spectral filter arrays (MSFA) [22, 25]. MSFA-based cameras are a useful option
54 for the manufacturing of a multi-spectral camera with a few channels (typically three to six) that takes
55 full snapshot. The authors in [22] provide a review on multi-spectral acquisition systems, and report the
56 development of a custom made spectral device. The authors display the difficulties of using the results from
57 a filter optimisation process to build a custom-made camera, because of the current limitations that exist in
58 the manufacturing processes. In [25], the authors performed a simulation of a MSFA-based imaging sensor
59 for spectral reconstruction, focusing on how to optimise the response of filter arrays and demosaicing. All
60 these studies are good examples of how it is possible to build multi-spectral cameras, and they manifest that
61 the theoretical response of selected wavelengths (by optimisation or other means) is not easy to reproduce.

62 This paper develops a new methodology for filter selection using machine learning techniques to fill a gap
63 between the two exposed approaches: the broadly studied wavelength band-selection by optimisation; and
64 considering the design and usage of optical filters instead of selecting specific bands. Using HSI data acquired
65 from an UGV for the purpose of mango ripeness estimation, the methodology developed here simulates the
66 potential for lower cost multi-spectral solutions to the same problem, by optimising the selection of lower
67 cost camera/filter combinations. The prediction of dry matter (DM) is a desirable goal in mango industry, as
68 it is considered an important indicator for fruit ripeness [44]. Proximal HSI has already been demonstrated
69 to be an effective tool for the automatic estimation of DM in mango orchards [48], hence we sought to
70 understand the trade-off necessary to develop a multi-spectral solution (*e.g.*, with the need of reducing the
71 spectral dimensionality) while maintaining a good response in prediction. The underlying approach could
72 also be adapted for specific objectives beyond ripeness estimation.

73 2. Materials and methods

74 The analysis performed in this study used as input the same data obtained in [48], for mango ripeness
75 estimation, [validating the DM content with a hand-held NIR spectrometer already tested in other works](#)
76 [\[2, 7\]](#). HSI on mangoes was performed under field conditions from a UGV and used to simulate expected
77 performance with single and multi-spectral sensor systems, with a view to cost reduction. The optimal single-

78 sensor solution identified from simulation was also verified with the matching real-world (non-simulated)
79 device.

80 The methodological pipeline followed in this study is displayed in Fig. 1. The simulated multi-spectral
81 sensors were: 1) a device with one monochrome camera sensor and one filter in front of it (Fig. 1a), 2)
82 a device with one RGB sensor and one filter in front of it (Fig. 1b), and finally 3) a device with four
83 different monochrome sensors (a typical configuration in retail multi-spectral cameras), each one of them
84 with a different filter (Fig. 1c). Filter responses were obtained by multiplying the reflectance spectra (from
85 HSI and after correction) by the filter transmittance profile, and then integrating. Two different filter pools
86 were tested: 1) theoretical, parametrically defined filters and 2) actual commercial off-the-shelf (COTS)
87 filters with filter responses defined in commercial datasheets (Fig. 1d). The filter selection optimisation was
88 performed by GAs, which we propose as a more generally computationally tractable solution, while also
89 verified by a more expensive brute force approach (Fig. 1e).

90 The first device (Fig. 1a), an RGB sensor with one filter (Fig. 1b), was simulated by testing all the
91 filters from the COTS pool using SVMs in a brute force approach. The same flow was followed for the
92 device with a monochrome camera sensor, the only difference being that simple linear regression was used
93 for modelling due to the one-dimensional input that is generated. Finally, data were obtained from a real
94 camera with the optimal IR cut filter identified and compared to [the simulation of an RGB camera \(from
95 red, green and blue colour bands recorded by the hyperspectral camera\) with the same IR cut filter. This
96 comparison was used to validate the accuracy of the simulated filters.](#)

97 Models from RGB data were also developed and compared with real RGB imaging, to verify the validity
98 of the simulation. The filter selection for the four-sensor device (Fig. 1c) was performed by GAs two times:
99 one from parametric filters and one from COTS filters. All permutations of filter combinations were tested
100 using a brute force approach, to validate the proposed GA approach.

101 2.1. Data collection

102 Data acquisition was carried out in a mango orchard (*Mangifera indica L.*) located in Bundaberg, Queens-
103 land, Australia, on the 6th of December, 2017. Seventy-eight mango fruits were selected assuring a large
104 variability in DM values. [Fig. 2 shows a histogram of the mango DM values, ranging from less than 10 to
105 21.5% m/m \(\$\mu = 12.98\% w/w, \sigma = 2.39\% w/w\$ \).](#) Mangoes were distributed in five fruit trays for spectral
106 acquisition (Fig. 3b).

107 A hand-held NIR spectrometer (Felix F-750, Felix Instruments Inc., Camas, USA) was employed as
108 reference method for DM content. [This device uses a Zeiss MMS1 NIR sensor with a spectral range from
109 400 to 1100 nm, having pixel and optical resolutions of 10 and 3.3 nm respectively. Radiometric calibration is
110 performed by referencing on every measurement from an internal halogen lamp and background illumination.](#)
111 [The spectrometer was calibrated prior to use following the instructions from the manufacturer \[10\], with
112 validation \$R^2 = 0.95\$, and \$RMSE = 0.56\% w/w\$. The performance of this instrument for mango DM
113 estimation was already proven by other authors in different experiments \[2, 7\].](#)

114 A general purpose unmanned ground vehicle (UGV), developed at the Australian Centre for Field
115 Robotics and called “Shrimp”, was used for HSI and RGB image data acquisition (Fig. 3). The vehi-
116 cle was equipped with a Resonon Pika II Vis-NIR hyperspectral line-scan camera (Resonon, Inc., Bozeman,

Figure 1: The simulation of three different kinds of lower cost single and multi-spectral sensors for ripeness estimation was carried out from HSI on mangoes performed under field conditions from a UGV. The simulated spectral devices were: an RGB sensor with one filter in front of it (a), a monochrome camera with one filter in front of it (b) and finally a system of four monochrome sensors (a typical configuration in retail multi-spectral cameras), each with a different filter (c). Filters were selected from two different pools (d) and using two different selection methodologies (e).

117 USA), shown in Fig. 3a, that has 648 spatial dimensions (pixels) and 244 spectral datapoints with a depth
 118 of 12 bits and covering the Vis-NIR range from approximately 390 to 890 nm (spectral resolution of 2 nm).
 119 HSI data acquisition was configured to be performed at different times and to measure both mango sides,
 120 after manual rotation of each fruit in the trays. Several illumination reference panels (QPcard 102) were
 121 placed adjacent to the trays for radiometric calibration (Fig. 3b). At the same time as HSI scanning, an
 122 RGB camera was used for image acquisition of the fruit in the trays. A Prosilica GT3300C camera (Allied
 123 Vision Technologies GmbH, Stadtroda, Germany) was employed (Fig. 3a), with a NIR cut filter SP700¹
 124 mounted [27], and in synchronisation with four Excelitas MVS-5000 strobe lights (Excelitas Technologies
 125 Corp., Waltham, USA), as described in [37]. The system has been demonstrated to be effective for scanning
 126 ripeness in whole orchards [48, 37], but for this work it was used to scan the trays seen in Fig. 3b.

127 Illumination compensation was applied to the hyperspectral data. In the first place, the raw HSI data

¹The SP700 is a relatively standard IR cut filter as commonly used in standard RGB cameras. This filter discards the small NIR sensitivity present in common RGB filters (small heap starting from around 800 nm in the blue line in Fig. 4.)

Figure 2: Histogram of the dry matter values from the mango samples measured by the hyperspectral camera.

Figure 3: Picture of the unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) and the RGB and hyperspectral cameras (a) and the UGV during data acquisition upon the mango trays (b).

128 was transformed to at-sensor radiance using the following formula from [40]:

$$I_s(\lambda) = \frac{dn_s(\lambda) - dn_{sdc}(\lambda)}{dn_{ff}(\lambda) - dn_{ffdc}(\lambda)} I_{ff}(\lambda) \quad (1)$$

129 where $dn_s(\lambda)$ is raw digital number (DN) values of the sample s at a wavelength λ , $dn_{sdc}(\lambda)$ is DN values of

130 dark current; while $\mathbf{dn}_{\text{ff}}(\lambda)$ and $\mathbf{dn}_{\text{ffdc}}(\lambda)$ are flat field DN values acquired using an integrating sphere and
131 corresponding dark current, respectively. $\mathbf{I}_{\text{ff}}(\lambda)$ corresponds to the internal radiance values of the integrating
132 sphere. Finally, after applying the “LOGSEP” method described by [47] and [8], the values were converted to
133 reflectance. This pre-processing was carried out to account for the effects of non-uniform lens transmittance
134 and sensor quantum efficiency. For further details on data collection and spectral preprocessing, the reader
135 is referred to [47] and, especially, to [48], as mango DM estimation using ground-based HSI is presented in
136 that paper, and the same dataset was used for filter selection in the present study.

137 2.2. Dataset building and model development

138 Having 78 mangoes and two scanned sides per fruit, the final dataset comprised a total of 156 samples.
139 Each sample contained the full average spectrum from the visible side of the mango and its corresponding
140 DM value as measured with the hand-held spectrometer described in Section 2.1.

141 Except where indicated otherwise, all the models developed in this study were trained using Epsilon-
142 Support Vector Machines (ε -SVMs) as regressors from the Support Vector Regression (SVR) implementation
143 in scikit-learn 0.19.1 [33], using the default values provided by the library for the hyperparameters.

144 The selection of ε -SVMs and the hyperparameter values set was carried out after intensive supervised
145 testing of different algorithms and hyperparameter configurations upon the original 156-samples dataset, and
146 based on our knowledge and experience using machine learning techniques for this kind of data input. We
147 want to highlight that, within the spectral filter design methodology described in this paper, the selection
148 of an adequate classifier or regressor depends on the target problem (in our case, DM estimation from
149 HSI), and other methodologies may be applied.

150 Models were validated using five iterations of 5-fold cross validation (CV). Each one of the CV iterations
151 used a different random number generator seed for fold splitting. Still, the same five seeds were used at each
152 model development in this study to ensure that performance differences are due only to the input used, not
153 the random distribution of the samples in the folds.

154 2.3. Filter selection

155 2.3.1. RGB and monochrome sensors

156 The monochrome device was simulated by testing all the filters from a pool of 96 COTS filters from
157 MIDOPT [27], using a brute force approach. The list of model numbers can be found in Table 1. Filter data
158 specifications—transmission data within the range of the hyperspectral camera used in this study—were
159 obtained from the manufacturer web-site [27]. When using one filter in a monochrome device, only one
160 intensity value is produced per pixel. Therefore, a simple linear regression between this intensity and mango
161 DM was used for modelling.

162 A device with one RGB sensor and one filter in front of it was simulated in order to see how filtered RGB
163 imaging is correlated with DM content in mangoes. From the HSI spectra, their RGB information (red,
164 green and blue channels) was extracted using the quantum efficiency data from the Prosilica GT3300C (Fig.
165 4), provided by the manufacturer in [1]. The three quantum efficiency profiles were normalised to the unit
166 to be used as the RGB sensitivity values, and then applied separately to the HSI raw spectra. Afterwards,

Figure 4: Quantum efficiency of the RGB filters assembled in the Prosilica GT3300C [1]. These filters were used to simulate a expected response from the hyperspectral images.

167 as in the monochrome device, all 96 COTS filters were tested in a brute force approach, applying each one
 168 of them to the three RGB channels.

169 Mango ripeness estimation from RGB was carried out for both HSI (RGB_{HSI}) and real Prosilica RGB
 170 imaging ($RGB_{RGB-Camera}$). This was tested as data was also available from real (not simulated) RGB
 171 camera with a MIDOPT IR cut filter, and these were compared to the simulated counterpart to validate the
 172 simulation approach.. Additionally, to test how well the RGB information from HSI was extracted (using
 173 the filters in Fig. 4), the correlation between RGB_{HSI} and $RGB_{RGB-Camera}$ was tested after transformation
 174 from the RGB to the HSV (hue, saturation, value) colour space.

175 2.3.2. Four monochrome sensors

176 A device with four different monochrome sensors, each one of them with a different filter, was simulated,
 177 as this is a typical configuration in low-cost, retail multi-spectral cameras. Two independent pools were
 178 used for filter selection. The first pool was generated from parametric (hypothetical) filters, by fine tuning
 179 the corresponding parameters. The transmittance for each filter was generated from a normal distribution
 180 (with maximum in 1) defined by: its central wavelength in nm ($C_N \in [390, 890]$); its bandwidth in nm
 181 ($B_N \in [6, 492]$); and the type of filter ($T_N \in \{\text{bandpass, longpass, shortpass}\}$). Each filter is individually
 182 applied to the raw average spectra from the HSI data of each mango, obtaining four scalars representing
 183 the four filter responses. Therefore, the goal was to select the best four parametric filter combination that
 184 maximise the DM prediction capability.

185 The second filter pool was built from the same 96 COTS filters described in Section 2.3.1. The advantage
 186 to do this is that these filters are known to be feasible to construct and easy to obtain, whereas there is no
 187 guarantee that the optimal parametric filters would be practical. The goal again was to select the best four
 188 COTS filter combination that maximise the DM prediction capability.

189 Therefore, for each filter pool, two optimisation problems were defined. For parametric filters:

$$\arg \max_P f(C_1, B_1, T_1, C_2, B_2, T_2, C_3, B_3, T_3, C_4, B_4, T_4) \quad (2)$$

190 where f and is a fitness function that, given the 12 parameters (to define four filters), returns the R^2 score
 191 after applying the four filters to the HSI dataset and validating the models as described in Section 2.2.

192 For COTS filters:

$$\arg \max_P g(F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4) \quad (3)$$

193 where g is a fitness function that, given four different filters F_N , returns the R^2 score (for regression to
 194 dry matter) after applying them to the HSI dataset and validating the models as described in Section 2.2.
 195 [Further details about the algorithms implementing the \$f\$ and \$g\$ functions can be found in Supplementary](#)
 196 [Material.](#)

197 Although, by definition, C_N and B_N are real numbers expressed in nm, their values are represented as
 198 integers by the data from the HSI camera hardware, because of the integer binning in the spectral dimension
 199 (indices in an array). This, along with the fact that T_N and F_N are categorical variables, makes f and
 200 g non-continuous functions. For this reason, optimisation techniques based on derivatives or gradients
 201 cannot be used. A CHC-based genetic algorithm [9] was implemented for the parameter optimisation
 202 of f and g within the ranges defined for each variable. CHC algorithm (cross-generational elitist selection;
 203 heterogeneous recombination; cataclysmic mutation) is capable of providing a wide solution exploration—by
 204 keeping relatively small individual populations frequently reinitialised—while still maximising exploitation
 205 within a population.

206 CHC starts by setting a population of M individuals randomly initialised and a convergence value δ of $\frac{|P|}{4}$.
 207 At each iteration, $M/2$ crossovers are performed by randomly picking two parents (without replacement) and,
 208 if there is enough genetic difference between them (incest prevention), performing a half uniform crossover
 209 [9]. The best M individuals from the offspring and the original population are selected, and the cycle is
 210 repeated. If no offspring was generated, δ is decreased by one. If $\delta < 0$, the population is removed and
 211 replaced only keeping the best individual and adding $M - 1$ randomly initialised individuals, also resetting
 212 δ to $\frac{|P|}{4}$ (cataclysmic mutation).

213 The number of individuals in the population M was set to 40, ten times the number of filters, and the
 214 number of generations was set to 500. To analyse the convergence capability of GAs for filter selection, a
 215 hundred iterations of CHC were performed, selecting, from each one of them, the best individual from the
 216 last generation.

217 Additionally, a brute force procedure was designed to test a large number of filter combinations and
 218 to select one with the highest performance. In the case of parametric filters, these combinations were
 219 generated from constraining the three filter parameters into fixed values. Specifically, CW_N were constrained
 220 to take 16 equidistant values between 390 and 890 nm; BW_N , two different values: 64 and 186 nm; and
 221 T_N took the three values “bandpass”, “longpass” and “shortpass”. [The bandwidth values were selected](#)
 222 [according to available options that can be commonly found in commercial filters, while the 16 values for](#)
 223 [the central wavelengths were picked in a constant basis to cover most of the spectral range of interest](#)

224 and to avoid missing wavelengths within it. All these possible values ($16 \times 2 \times 3$) made up a total of 96
 225 different filters to be used. From these, all four filter combinations with repetitions were tested, resulting in
 226 $\binom{n}{k} = \binom{n+k-1}{k} = 3,764,376$ tests, for $n = 96$ and $k = 4$. In the case of COTS filters, as the pool contained
 227 96 models, a brute force approach was also carried out, resulting in a similar number of tests performed.

228 All data processing was coded using multi-threading in Python 2.7.12, in an Intel[®] Core[™]i7-6700 CPU
 229 (8 cores, 3.40 GHz) with 32 GB of RAM. For parametric filters, the 100 GA runs took approximately 13.3
 230 hours to complete, and the brute force evaluation lasted for 22.3 hours. For COTS filters, the 100 GA runs
 231 took 8.3 hours, while the brute force methodology took 18.5 hours.

232 3. Results

233 3.1. Mango spectra

234 Fig. 5 displays the reflectance plots of the 156 mango spectra used in the simulations. Reflectance values
 235 ranged from slightly higher than zero and over 0.8. The spectral profiles have certain similarities with those
 236 from other vegetative measurements, like leaves or fruit. These similarities are larger from the characteristic
 237 reflectance jump around 700 nm to NIR wavelengths. Most spectrum variations can be found between 500
 238 and 680 nm, a range corresponding to colours that can be present in mango skin at different maturity stages.

Figure 5: Reflectance plot of the 156 mango spectra acquired under field conditions with a hyperspectral camera from and unmanned ground vehicle. Each spectrum came from averaging all the pixels (spectra) corresponding to each sample (mango).

239 3.2. RGB and monochrome sensors

240 To test the accuracy in the extraction of the RGB information from all the samples for the hyperspectral
 241 camera, the correlation between this and Prosilica RGB imaging was computed, using the hue channel from
 242 HSV space, as shown in Fig. 6. A high correlation was observed with an R^2 score of 0.89. Mango DM
 243 prediction models were developed using the three-dimensional RGB input from both imagers, returning R^2
 244 values of 0.55 from RGB_{HSI} and 0.63 from $RGB_{RGB-Camera}$.

Figure 6: Correlations between the Prosilica RGB camera ($RGB_{RGB-Camera}$) and hyperspectral data (RGB_{HSI}) for hue after converting to HSV. HSV values were converted from RGB data provided by the Prosilica GT3300 images and after applying the RGB filters in Fig. 4 to hyperspectral data. Each dot represent colour information from the same mango sample.

245 The results from the brute force approach on the monochrome sensor are presented in Table 1 (column
 246 “Monochrome sensor”). The performance values were, in the vast majority of cases, below the 0.2 mark of
 247 R^2 (93 out of 96 filters). Only bandpass filters around the 660 nm wavelength revealed a better response for
 248 DM estimation, with a peak of 0.40 at BP660 and two shoulders of 0.27 around it, at BP635 and BP695.

249 The results from the simulation of a RGB sensor with one filter are shown in Table 1 (column “RGB
 250 sensor”). The overall trend was much higher than using a monochrome sensor. Half of the filters yielded R^2
 251 scores above 0.50, and three of them (BP550, SP700 and SP701) reached 0.61, very similar to the performance
 252 of unfiltered $RGB_{RGB-Camera}$. It is noteworthy that the $RGB_{RGB-Camera}$ result previously exposed (R^2 of
 253 0.63), obtained with a SP700 filter mounted in front of the RGB camera, agrees with the simulation of
 254 RGB_{HSI} with the same filter (Table 1, column “RGB sensor”), that resulted in an R^2 of 0.61.

255 3.3. Four monochrome sensors

256 Results for the selection of four filters in the simulation of a device with four monochrome sensors and
 257 four filters are presented in this section. Results are divided into the selection of the best four parametric
 258 filters and the best COTS filters. When analysing all the R^2 values reported here, the 0.74 outcome from
 259 the DM estimation using the whole HSI spectrum [48] should be taken into consideration as the theoretical
 260 maximum performing baseline.

261 3.3.1. Parametric filter selection

262 From the 100 GA runs for the selection of parametric filters, the best individual (set of four filters)
 263 from the last generation was picked and considered to be the best solution. The average R^2 of these 100
 264 individuals was 0.68, with a standard variation $\sigma = 0.004$ that showed a high level of convergence from all
 265 the GA runs. Histograms are shown for the 100 GA solutions central wavelength (Fig. 7), bandwidth (Fig.
 266 8) and type of filter (Fig. 9). For the purpose of creating the histograms, for each individual the four filters
 267 were sorted by their central wavelength. Therefore, the first filter was the one with the leftmost central
 268 wavelength (lower nm values), while the fourth filter was the one with the higher central wavelengths values.

Figure 7: Histograms of the central wavelength of the best individuals from the optimisation with 100 genetic algorithm (GA) runs. Each individual corresponds to the best one from one GA optimisation, and comprises 4 different filters, from number 1 (a), to number 4 (d). For each individual, the four filters were sorted by their central wavelength. Therefore, (a) presents the filters with the leftmost central wavelength (lower nm values), while (d) contains the filters with the higher central wavelengths values.

269 The general trend shows that, for each parameter, all the filters had a clear convergence peak. This is
 270 specially clear for central wavelength, filter 1 (Fig. 7a) centred at 400 nm and filter 3 (Fig. 7c) centred
 271 at 650 nm; and for type of filter (Fig. 9), in which there was a strong preference toward bandpass for all
 272 the filters. More dispersion was found in the bandwidth histograms (Fig. 8), but still clear convergences
 273 towards narrow bandwidths were present in all cases.

274 From the brute force approach for parametric filter selection, the best result yielded a R^2 of 0.68, slightly
 275 lower than the best one of all the 100 GA runs (R^2 of 0.69). Fig. 10 shows the transmission data of the
 276 parametric filters selected by both method. In both cases, the central wavelengths of the four filters were
 277 extremely similar, but slightly narrower in the case of the GA optimisation (Fig. 10a). The third filter,
 278 a bandpass centred around 630 nm, was virtually the same exact one in both approaches, but the high
 279 similarity among all four filters highlights the importance of this spectral region.

280 3.3.2. Commercial filter selection

281 The average R^2 score from the 100 GA runs in the COTS filter selection was 0.66 ($\sigma < 0.001$). After
 282 alphabetically sorting the four filters of each individual, the histograms for the selected filters are shown in
 283 Fig. 11. A perfect convergence to filters AB555 and BP635 were achieved by all GA runs (Figs. 11a and
 284 b), and filters NF550 and SP510 were selected 97 out of 100 times in Figs. 11c and d.

Figure 8: Histograms of the bandwidth of the filters presented in Fig. 7.

Figure 9: Histogram of the type of the filters presented in Figs. 7.

Figure 10: Four parametric filters selected from the best individual from all the 100 genetic algorithm runs (a) and from the brute force approach (b). The R^2 displayed represent the performance of the mango dry matter estimation models after applying the filters to the hyperspectral data.

285 Fig. 12 shows all the filters selected by the 100 GA runs. In all cases, as also seen in the parametric
 286 filter selection (Section 3.3.1), the optimisation highly focused on wavelengths around 600-650 nm and at the
 287 beginning of the spectral range. The brute force approach, in which all possible COTS filter combinations
 288 with repetitions were tested, selected AB555, BP635, NF550 and SP510 as the best filter combination, with
 289 an R^2 of 0.66.

290 4. Discussion

291 This paper presented a new methodology for the selection of spectral filters for the estimation of ripeness
 292 in mangoes from in-field spectral acquisitions. While HSI for mango dry matter estimation was already
 293 demonstrated to be effective under the same conditions in [48], with a baseline R^2 of 0.74, the performance
 294 obtained from the multi-spectral sensor simulation in the present study was not far below, with R^2 scores
 295 up to 0.68. Both results can be directly compared side-by-side, because the input data were identical, and
 296 a similar validation process was used, with five iterations of 5-fold CV to compute the performance statis-
 297 tics. This provides evidence that for the task of mango ripeness estimation, a high level of dimensionality
 298 reduction can be performed to spectra within the range from 400 to 900 nm without greatly jeopardising
 299 the effectiveness of the machine learning models, although a small performance reduction from the complete
 300 HSI data was observed.

301 The results obtained from the simulation of a monochrome device with a single filter exhibited poor
 302 performance for all the filters tested (Table 1, R^2 below 0.10 in the majority of the cases), dissuading the
 303 consideration of this solution for DM prediction in mangoes. Yet still, it is worth paying special attention
 304 to those bandpass filters around the 660 nm wavelength (BP635, BP660 and BP695), for which the scores,
 305 although not good, were clearly higher than the remaining ones. Nevertheless, if a single device is the
 306 desired set-up, the best option would be to use a standard RGB camera, as suggested by the results from

Figure 11: Histogram of the determination coefficient (R^2) of the filter names from the best individuals obtained in the commercial filter optimisation with 100 genetic algorithm runs.

307 the simulation of a filtered RGB sensor in Table 1 (R^2 up to 0.61 with an SP700) and the actual validation
 308 using a real RGB camera with that filter (R^2 of 0.63). This similarity also demonstrated the correctness of
 309 the simulations when compared to the real sensor. It is no surprise that RGB imaging alone can be enough
 310 to get an acceptable prediction performance, as colour in mangoes is a good indicator of maturity for visual
 311 inspection. [In the case of the mango DM estimation problem addressed, depending on the level of accuracy
 312 sought, RGB alone \(with a NIR cut filter\) could be considered as an alternative good enough for maturity
 313 estimation.](#)

314 Filters around that spectral region were repeatedly selected when optimising for the four-sensor device.
 315 The filter selection performed from the parametric filter pool resulted in a high convergence toward the
 316 640 nm wavelength (Fig. 7c), while the filter BP635 was unanimously selected when optimising from
 317 the COTS filter pool (Fig. 11b). This implies that this region is crucial for the prediction of DM in
 318 mangoes, and if the development of multi-spectral camera is sought, the inclusion of a bandpass filter
 319 centred at approximately 640 nm is critical. The parametric filter selection also had very strong preferences
 320 toward lower wavelengths on or around 400 nm and 480 nm (Figs. 7a and b), and this, along with the
 321 preference for small bandwidth filters (Figs. 8 and 9), increased the importance of those narrow bands

Figure 12: Transmission data of the filters from the best individuals obtained in the commercial filter optimisation with 100 genetic algorithm runs.

322 in the electromagnetic spectrum. Seemingly, the COTS filter pool offered more limited options, and the
323 optimal solution from the optimisation using that pool would presumably respond worse than a filter selection
324 from parametric tuning. Nevertheless, as observed in the results in Section 3.3.2, the average performance
325 obtained from the COTS filter optimisation (R^2 of 0.66) was very similar than that from the parametric
326 filter optimisation (R^2 of 0.68), showing that for this application, there is no great potential advantage
327 to designing custom bespoke filters, beyond what is already available off the shelf. Similarly to the filter
328 selected in the simulation of a monochrome device, discussed above, both the parametric and commercial
329 solutions also gave strong importance to the same spectral regions, around 650 nm and 400-500 nm (Fig.
330 12). The identification of the transmittance shapes of several spectral filters (*i.e.*, parametric filter selection)
331 do indeed allow to obtain very fine (virtually, the best) solution for this application. Notwithstanding, in
332 the majority of the cases, these filters are based on theoretical transmittance data (typically from Gaussian
333 curves) with limited practical implementations [22], hence the selection of optimal COTS filters can be
334 considered as a more practical alternative. As demonstrated by the correlation between actual RGB_{HSI} and
335 $RGB_{\text{RGB-Camera}}$ (Fig. 6), the filter simulation in this paper can be assumed to be accurate enough for the
336 filters selected in the simulation of different spectral devices.

337 The design of the optimisation processes presented in this study has demonstrated suitability for this task,
 338 as the best solutions were obtained in virtually all cases. The preference for running a hundred iterations
 339 was chosen for the analysis of the convergence capability of GAs, to see if they indeed converge to a global
 340 maximum, or get stuck in a local one. In the case of the parametric filter selection (Section 3.3.1), this
 341 convergence was almost perfect in terms of the average fitness result obtained in the last generation of each
 342 GA run. An R^2 of 0.68 was obtained in virtually all runs, supported by the low standard deviation of these
 343 results ($\sigma = 0.004$), meaning that a global maximum was reached. Nevertheless, very similar fitness values
 344 were obtained from slightly different values for the optimised parameters. For example, considering the fourth
 345 filter, values for central wavelength (Fig. 7d) were not completely focused in narrow ranges, and the same
 346 occurred for bandwidth (Fig. 8d), in which, although low bandwidths were preferred, many other values were
 347 also picked at some iterations. These different solution options show that several parameter configurations
 348 are valid and could lead to optimal performance. Still, the analysis of the parameter histograms from the
 349 100 optimisation runs helps to see the tendency of GAs toward specific values (the most common ones), and
 350 thus to focus on those when translating the results to practical implementations. The optimisation using
 351 the COTS filter pool converged even more tightly, as the average R^2 value of 0.66 was accompanied by
 352 extremely low standard deviation, below 0.001. The best solution was almost unanimously selected (filter
 353 models AB555, BP635, NF550 and SP510), making this a clear option for consideration. In summary, all
 354 these results bolster that the choice of GA optimisation is a reliable option for spectral filter selection.

355 The suitability of GAs to solve the objective presented in this paper is not only supported by the analysis
 356 of their performance, but also by comparing the outcomes with naive, brute force results. A true, complete
 357 brute force approach for parametric filter selection was impossible to carry out. The parameters CW_N and
 358 BW_N could potentially take any wavelength value between 400 and 900 nm that, coded as integers, lead
 359 to 244 different values for each one of them (the 244 spectral datapoints that represent the hyperspectral
 360 camera's spectral range), while T_N can take three different values. Considering that four filters need to
 361 be optimised, the total number of combinations is intractably large. For this reason, a subset of these
 362 combinations that covers all the ranges had to be used. This explains why the best solution from this brute
 363 force approach (Fig. 10b) was slightly lower than the best solution from the 100 optimisation runs (Fig. 10a),
 364 R^2 of 0.68 vs. 0.69. Still, the solutions lied within the same central wavelengths, bandwidths and bandpass
 365 filter types, as illustrated in Fig. 10, raising GAs as a completely capable alternative for the optimal selection
 366 of filters in a reduced fraction of time. The limited number of options in the COTS filter tools made the
 367 full brute force approach feasible, testing more than three and a half millions of combinations. The best
 368 solution from these was exactly the same one selected in the vast majority of the 100 GA runs (Fig. 11),
 369 therefore a single optimisation run would likely select the best solution for COTS filter selection, similarly
 370 to a brute force approach, but in less than 20 minutes vs. more than 18 hours. Whether for parametric
 371 or COTS filter selection, brute force approaches selected four filters from relatively small pools, and this
 372 made it possible to test all the combinations within reasonable times (less than 24 hours of computing,
 373 each filter set evaluation taking 0.02 seconds). If, instead of 96, the filter pool would have been doubled,
 374 almost two full weeks of computation would have been necessary to test all the valid combinations with
 375 brute force. Furthermore, if the same 96 filter pool is maintained, but five filter combinations are tested, the
 376 total number of $\binom{96}{5} = 71,523,144$ would have taken 16 days to complete. Optimisation, as opposed to

377 brute force calculation, regardless of the metaheuristic selected, becomes then mandatory for filter selection,
378 and this study demonstrated that GAs provides a stable choice for the optimisation methodology.

379 The methodology described in this paper could be used as a guideline for a spectral filter design procedure,
380 in a stage previous to hardware selection and assembling. The described pipeline should be adapted in those
381 steps that depend on the specific nature of the problem to solve. For example, the training of prediction
382 models needs to be analysed and defined (considering different strategies, algorithms, validation procedures,
383 etc.); other different kinds of spectral filters may be simulated, having new parameters to optimise; or even
384 the total number of sensors may vary (*e.g.*, optical devices with 3 or 5 sensors and filters). The results
385 from the simulations could therefore be aggregated to a hardware selection step, considering the current
386 alternatives and their cost vs. the potential cost and performance of the simulated devices.

387 5. Conclusions

388 This paper presented a new alternative for the selection of spectral filters to estimate mango ripeness from
389 hyperspectral imaging acquired in-field from an unmanned ground vehicle. The selection was carried out not
390 by specific band picking, as commonly described in the HSI literature, but simulating several multi-spectral
391 sensors with filters having different transmittance responses, using parametric and commercial filter pools.
392 The simulations and analyses of several different devices demonstrated that, by converting the goal into an
393 optimisation problem, genetic algorithms were able to obtain the best solution for dry matter prediction
394 more efficiently than using brute force approaches. While HSI was already demonstrated to be adequate
395 for ripeness estimation in mangoes, the results in this paper show that dimensionality reduction is feasible
396 while still maintaining an acceptable performance of the prediction models. This allows future work towards
397 building lower cost devices that are customised towards monitoring specific traits with relevance to precision
398 agriculture, and for mango dry matter specifically.

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404 References

- 405 [1] ALLIED VISION TECHNOLOGIES GMBH. Prosilica GT3300 specifications. [https://www.alliedvision.com/en/products/
406 cameras/detail/Prosilica%20GT/3300.html](https://www.alliedvision.com/en/products/cameras/detail/Prosilica%20GT/3300.html). Accessed: 2018-11-21.
- 407 [2] ANDERSON, N. T., SUBEDI, P. P., AND WALSH, K. B. Manipulation of mango fruit dry matter content to improve eating
408 quality. *Scientia Horticulturae* 226 (2017), 316–321.
- 409 [3] BODNER, G., NAKHFOROOSH, A., ARNOLD, T., AND LEITNER, D. Hyperspectral imaging: a novel approach for plant root
410 phenotyping. *Plant methods* 14, 1 (2018), 84.
- 411 [4] CHANG, Y.-L., LIU, J.-N., CHEN, Y.-L., CHANG, W.-Y., HSIEH, T.-J., AND HUANG, B. Hyperspectral band selection
412 based on parallel particle swarm optimization and impurity function band prioritization schemes. *Journal of Applied
413 Remote Sensing* 8, 1 (2014), 084798.

- 414 [5] DEERY, D., JIMENEZ-BERNI, J., JONES, H., SIRAULT, X., AND FURBANK, R. Proximal remote sensing buggies and potential
415 applications for field-based phenotyping. *Agronomy* 4, 3 (2014), 349–379.
- 416 [6] DIAGO, M. P., FERNÁNDEZ-NOVALES, J., FERNANDES, A. M., MELO-PINTO, P., AND TARDAGUILA, J. Use of visible and
417 short-wave near-infrared hyperspectral imaging to fingerprint anthocyanins in intact grape berries. *Journal of agricultural
418 and food chemistry* 64, 40 (2016), 7658–7666.
- 419 [7] DOS SANTOS NETO, J. P., DE ASSIS, M. W. D., CASAGRANDE, I. P., JÚNIOR, L. C. C., AND DE ALMEIDA TEIXEIRA, G. H.
420 Determination of ‘Palmer’ mango maturity indices using portable near infrared (VIS-NIR) spectrometer. *Postharvest
421 Biology and Technology* 130 (2017), 75–80.
- 422 [8] DREW, M. S., AND FINLAYSON, G. D. Analytic solution for separating spectra into illumination and surface reflectance
423 components. *JOSA A* 24, 2 (2007), 294–303.
- 424 [9] ESHELMAN, L. J. The chc adaptive search algorithm: How to have safe search when engaging in nontraditional genetic
425 recombination. In *Foundations of genetic algorithms*, vol. 1. Elsevier, 1991, pp. 265–283.
- 426 [10] FELIX INSTRUMENTS, INC. Mango data collection standard operating procedure. [https://felixinstruments.com/static/
427 media/uploads/mango_data-collection_sop.pdf](https://felixinstruments.com/static/media/uploads/mango_data-collection_sop.pdf). Accessed: 2019-05-30.
- 428 [11] FERNANDES, A. M., MELO-PINTO, P., MILLAN, B., TARDÁGUILA, J., AND DIAGO, M. P. Automatic discrimination of
429 grapevine (*vitis vinifera* l.) clones using leaf hyperspectral imaging and partial least squares. *The Journal of Agricultural
430 Science* 153, 3 (2015), 455–465.
- 431 [12] GANESAN, V. S. K., AND VASUKI, S. Maximin distance based band selection for endmember extraction in hyperspectral
432 images using simplex growing algorithm. *Multimedia Tools and Applications* 77, 6 (2018), 7221–7237.
- 433 [13] GAO, J., DU, Q., GAO, L., SUN, X., AND ZHANG, B. Ant colony optimization-based supervised and unsupervised band
434 selections for hyperspectral urban data classification. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing* 8, 1 (2014), 085094.
- 435 [14] GIOVENZANA, V., BEGHI, R., PARISI, S., BRANCADORO, L., AND GUIDETTI, R. Potential effectiveness of visible and near
436 infrared spectroscopy coupled with wavelength selection for real time grapevine leaf water status measurement. *Journal
437 of the Science of Food and Agriculture* 98, 5 (2018), 1935–1943.
- 438 [15] GUTIÉRREZ, S., FERNÁNDEZ-NOVALES, J., DIAGO, M. P., AND TARDAGUILA, J. On-the-go hyperspectral imaging under
439 field conditions and machine learning for the classification of grapevine varieties. *Frontiers in plant science* 9 (2018).
- 440 [16] GUTIÉRREZ, S., WENDEL, A., AND UNDERWOOD, J. Ground based hyperspectral imaging for extensive mango yield
441 estimation. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 157 (2019), 126–135.
- 442 [17] HANEISHI, H., HASEGAWA, T., HOSOI, A., YOKOYAMA, Y., TSUMURA, N., AND MIYAKE, Y. System design for accurately
443 estimating the spectral reflectance of art paintings. *Applied Optics* 39, 35 (2000), 6621–6632.
- 444 [18] HARDEBERG, J. Y. Filter selection for multispectral color image acquisition. *Journal of Imaging Science and Technology*
445 48, 2 (2004), 105–110.
- 446 [19] HUANG, L., ZHOU, Y., MENG, L., WU, D., AND HE, Y. Comparison of different ccd detectors and chemometrics for
447 predicting total anthocyanin content and antioxidant activity of mulberry fruit using visible and near infrared hyperspectral
448 imaging technique. *Food chemistry* 224 (2017), 1–10.
- 449 [20] HUANG, P., LUO, X., JIN, J., WANG, L., ZHANG, L., LIU, J., AND ZHANG, Z. Improving high-throughput phenotyping
450 using fusion of close-range hyperspectral camera and low-cost depth sensor. *Sensors* 18, 8 (2018), 2711.
- 451 [21] IMAI, F. H., QUAN, S., ROSEN, M. R., AND BERNS, R. S. Digital camera filter design for colorimetric and spectral accuracy.
452 In *Proc. of third international conference on multispectral color science* (2001), University of Joensuu, Finland, pp. 13–16.
- 453 [22] LAPRAY, P.-J., WANG, X., THOMAS, J.-B., AND GOUTON, P. Multispectral filter arrays: Recent advances and practical
454 implementation. *Sensors* 14, 11 (2014), 21626–21659.
- 455 [23] LI, S., QIU, J., YANG, X., LIU, H., WAN, D., AND ZHU, Y. A novel approach to hyperspectral band selection based on
456 spectral shape similarity analysis and fast branch and bound search. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*
457 27 (2014), 241–250.
- 458 [24] LI, X., WEI, Y., XU, J., FENG, X., WU, F., ZHOU, R., JIN, J., XU, K., YU, X., AND HE, Y. Ssc and ph for sweet assessment
459 and maturity classification of harvested cherry fruit based on nir hyperspectral imaging technology. *Postharvest Biology
460 and Technology* 143 (2018), 112–118.
- 461 [25] LI, Y., MAJUMDER, A., ZHANG, H., AND GOPI, M. Optimized multi-spectral filter array based imaging of natural scenes.
462 *Sensors* 18, 4 (2018), 1172.
- 463 [26] LIU, Z.-Y., QI, J.-G., WANG, N.-N., ZHU, Z.-R., LUO, J., LIU, L.-J., TANG, J., AND CHENG, J.-A. Hyperspectral dis-

- 464 crimination of foliar biotic damages in rice using principal component analysis and probabilistic neural network. *Precision*
465 *Agriculture* (2018), 1–19.
- 466 [27] MIDWEST OPTICAL SYSTEMS, INC. MIDOPT commercial filter specifications used in this study. [http://midopt.com/](http://midopt.com/filters/)
467 [filters/](http://midopt.com/filters/). Accessed: 2018-11-21.
- 468 [28] MOGHIMI, A., YANG, C., MILLER, M. E., KIANIAN, S. F., AND MARCHETTO, P. M. A novel approach to assess salt stress
469 tolerance in wheat using hyperspectral imaging. *Frontiers in plant science* 9 (2018).
- 470 [29] MOREL, J., JAY, S., FÉRET, J.-B., BAKACHE, A., BENDOULA, R., CARREEL, F., AND GORRETTA, N. Exploring the
471 potential of procosine and close-range hyperspectral imaging to study the effects of fungal diseases on leaf physiology.
472 *Scientific reports* 8, 1 (2018), 15933.
- 473 [30] NAGASUBRAMANIAN, K., JONES, S., SARKAR, S., SINGH, A. K., SINGH, A., AND GANAPATHYSUBRAMANIAN, B. Hyperspec-
474 tral band selection using genetic algorithm and support vector machines for early identification of charcoal rot disease in
475 soybean stems. *Plant methods* 14, 1 (2018), 86.
- 476 [31] PARK, B., AND LU, R. *Hyperspectral imaging technology in food and agriculture*. Springer, 2015.
- 477 [32] PAUL, A., BHATTACHARYA, S., DUTTA, D., SHARMA, J. R., AND DADHWAL, V. K. Band selection in hyperspectral imagery
478 using spatial cluster mean and genetic algorithms. *GIScience & Remote Sensing* 52, 6 (2015), 643–659.
- 479 [33] PEDREGOSA, F., VAROQUAUX, G., GRAMFORT, A., MICHEL, V., THIRION, B., GRISEL, O., BLONDEL, M., PRETTENHOFER,
480 P., WEISS, R., DUBOURG, V., VANDERPLAS, J., PASSOS, A., COURNAPEAU, D., BRUCHER, M., PERROT, M., AND DUCHES-
481 NAY, E. Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 12 (2011), 2825–2830.
- 482 [34] PÉGUILLLET, H., THOMAS, J.-B., GOUTON, P., AND RUCHEK, Y. Energy balance in single exposure multispectral sensors.
483 In *Colour and Visual Computing Symposium (CVCS), 2013* (2013), IEEE, pp. 1–6.
- 484 [35] RUNGPICHAYAPICHET, P., NAGLE, M., YUWANBUN, P., KHUWIJITJARU, P., MAHAYOTHEE, B., AND MÜLLER, J. Prediction
485 mapping of physicochemical properties in mango by hyperspectral imaging. *Biosystems Engineering* 159 (2017), 109–120.
- 486 [36] SKOOG, D. A., HOLLER, F. J., AND CROUCH, S. R. *Principles of instrumental analysis*. Cengage learning, 2017.
- 487 [37] STEIN, M., BARGOTI, S., AND UNDERWOOD, J. Image based mango fruit detection, localisation and yield estimation using
488 multiple view geometry. *Sensors* 16, 11 (2016), 1915.
- 489 [38] SUN, D.-W. *Hyperspectral imaging for food quality analysis and control*. Elsevier, 2010.
- 490 [39] SUN, X., YANG, L., SHEN, Q., NI, L., AND ZHANG, B. A new ant colony optimization algorithm based band selection
491 method. In *Hyperspectral Image and Signal Processing: Evolution in Remote Sensing (WHISPERS), 2014 6th Workshop*
492 *on* (2014), IEEE, pp. 1–4.
- 493 [40] SUOMALAINEN, J., ANDERS, N., IQBAL, S., ROERINK, G., FRANKE, J., WENTING, P., HÜNNIGER, D., BARTHOLOMEUS, H.,
494 BECKER, R., AND KOOISTRA, L. A lightweight hyperspectral mapping system and photogrammetric processing chain for
495 unmanned aerial vehicles. *Remote Sensing* 6, 11 (2014), 11013–11030.
- 496 [41] SUSIČ, N., ŽIBRAT, U., ŠIRCA, S., STRAJNAR, P., RAZINGER, J., KNAPIČ, M., VONČINA, A., UREK, G., AND STARE, B. G.
497 Discrimination between abiotic and biotic drought stress in tomatoes using hyperspectral imaging. *Sensors and Actuators*
498 *B: Chemical* 273 (2018), 842–852.
- 499 [42] TANG, K., XIE, L., AND LI, G. A multiple classifier system based on ant-colony optimization for hyperspectral image
500 classification. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (2017), vol. 787, IOP Publishing, p. 012011.
- 501 [43] TIAN, X., LI, J., WANG, Q., FAN, S., AND HUANG, W. A bi-layer model for nondestructive prediction of soluble solids
502 content in apple based on reflectance spectra and peel pigments. *Food chemistry* 239 (2018), 1055–1063.
- 503 [44] WALSH, K., AND SUBEDI, P. In-field monitoring of mango fruit dry matter for maturity estimation. In *XXIX International*
504 *Horticultural Congress on Horticulture: Sustaining Lives, Livelihoods and Landscapes (IHC2014): 1119* (2014), pp. 273–
505 278.
- 506 [45] WANG, X., THOMAS, J.-B., HARDEBERG, J. Y., AND GOUTON, P. A study on the impact of spectral characteristics
507 of filters on multispectral image acquisition. In *12th Congress of the International Colour Association* (2013), vol. 4,
508 pp. 1765–1768.
- 509 [46] WENDEL, A., AND UNDERWOOD, J. Extrinsic parameter calibration for line scanning cameras on ground vehicles with
510 navigation systems using a calibration pattern. *Sensors* 17, 11 (2017), 2491.
- 511 [47] WENDEL, A., AND UNDERWOOD, J. Illumination compensation in ground based hyperspectral imaging. *ISPRS Journal of*
512 *Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 129 (2017), 162–178.
- 513 [48] WENDEL, A., UNDERWOOD, J., AND WALSH, K. Maturity estimation of mangoes using hyperspectral imaging from a

- 514 ground based mobile platform. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 155 (2018), 298–313.
- 515 [49] WILLIAMS, D., BRITTEN, A., MCCALLUM, S., JONES, H., AITKENHEAD, M., KARLEY, A., LOADES, K., PRASHAR, A., AND
516 GRAHAM, J. A method for automatic segmentation and splitting of hyperspectral images of raspberry plants collected in
517 field conditions. *Plant methods* 13, 1 (2017), 74.
- 518 [50] XU, M., SHI, J., CHEN, W., SHEN, J., GAO, H., AND ZHAO, J. A band selection method for hyperspectral image based on
519 particle swarm optimization algorithm with dynamic sub-swarms. *Journal of Signal Processing Systems* (2018), 1–11.
- 520 [51] YASUMA, F., MITSUNAGA, T., ISO, D., AND NAYAR, S. K. Generalized assorted pixel camera: postcapture control of
521 resolution, dynamic range, and spectrum. *IEEE transactions on image processing* 19, 9 (2010), 2241–2253.
- 522 [52] ZHANG, M., GONG, M., AND CHAN, Y. Hyperspectral band selection based on multi-objective optimization with high
523 information and low redundancy. *Applied Soft Computing* 70 (2018), 604 – 621.
- 524 [53] ZHANG, M., MA, J., AND GONG, M. Unsupervised hyperspectral band selection by fuzzy clustering with particle swarm
525 optimization. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters* 14, 5 (2017), 773–777.
- 526 [54] ZHANG, Q., LI, Q., AND ZHANG, G. Rapid determination of leaf water content using vis/nir spectroscopy analysis with
527 wavelength selection. *Journal of Spectroscopy* 27, 2 (2012), 93–105.

Table 1: Determination coefficients (R^2) from applying one single commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) filter to raw reflectance spectrum in the range from 400 to 900 nm (Raw spectrum) or to apply one single COTS filter to a reflectance spectrum after applying RGB filters (RGB_{HSI}).

Filter applied	Monochrome sensor	RGB sensor	Filter applied	Monochrome sensor	RGB sensor
AB555	0.00	0.57	LP515	0.03	0.58
AC370	0.03	0.55	LP530	0.04	0.59
AC380	0.03	0.56	LP550	0.05	0.60
AC685	0.01	0.06	LP580	0.06	0.51
AC760	0.00	0.03	LP590	0.06	0.38
AC800	0.00	0.03	LP610	0.06	0.39
AC850	0.00	0.03	LP630	0.05	0.41
AC900	0.00	0.03	LP645	0.04	0.39
BP250	0.02	0.43	LP665	0.02	0.22
BP324	0.13	0.22	LP695	0.00	0.04
BP365	0.00	0.00	LP715	0.00	0.01
BP470	0.00	0.16	LP780	0.00	0.03
BP485	0.01	0.59	LP800	0.00	0.03
BP500	0.00	0.57	LP815	0.00	0.03
BP505	0.05	0.38	LP830	0.00	0.03
BP525	0.06	0.38	LP850	0.00	0.03
BP540	0.06	0.43	LP900	0.00	0.03
BP550	0.07	0.61	LP920	0.01	0.03
BP590	0.00	0.46	ND030	0.03	0.55
BP635	0.27	0.44	ND060	0.03	0.56
BP660	0.40	0.38	ND090	0.03	0.52
BP695	0.27	0.27	ND120	0.03	0.51
BP735	0.02	0.04	ND200	0.01	0.45
BP800	0.00	0.01	ND300	0.01	0.22
BP810	0.00	0.03	ND400	0.01	0.06
BP845	0.00	0.03	NF550	0.15	0.55
BP850	0.00	0.03	Ni030	0.03	0.55
BP865	0.00	0.03	Ni060	0.03	0.55
BP880	0.00	0.03	Ni090	0.03	0.56
DB395/870	0.00	0.00	Ni120	0.03	0.55
DB475/850	0.00	0.00	Ni200	0.02	0.54
DB550/850	0.02	0.26	PE530	0.00	0.57
DB660/850	0.09	0.55	SP510	0.00	0.02
DB735	0.01	0.53	SP570	0.03	0.39
DB850	0.01	0.59	SP585	0.01	0.26
DB940	0.02	0.60	SP625	0.00	0.56
FL550	0.03	0.55	SP635	0.01	0.59
LA080	0.03	0.56	SP644	0.01	0.58
LA120	0.04	0.59	SP645	0.01	0.59
LB080	0.01	0.50	SP650	0.01	0.59
LB120	0.01	0.51	SP675	0.03	0.60
LP285	0.03	0.55	SP700	0.07	0.61
LP330	0.03	0.55	SP701	0.08	0.61
LP340	0.03	0.55	SP705	0.04	0.59
LP390	0.03	0.55	SP730	0.08	0.60
LP415	0.03	0.56	SP785	0.06	0.58
LP470	0.03	0.58	TB475/550/850	0.01	0.27
LP500	0.03	0.58	TB550/660/850	0.01	0.60

R^2 values were obtained from five iterations of 5-fold cross validation using linear regression in the “Raw spectrum” column and support vector machines in “RGB” column. The names of the COTS filter models refer to [27]. As a general rule, the letters BP refer to “bandpass”, LP to “longpass”, SP to “shortpass”, ND and Ni to “neutral density”, LB to “light balancing” and AC to “acrylic”; while the number after the letters refer to the main central wavelength in nm.

(a)

(b)

Filter 1

(a)

Filter 2

(b)

Filter 3

(c)

Filter 4

(d)

Filter 1

(a)

Filter 2

(b)

Filter 3

(c)

Filter 4

(d)

Filter 1

(a)

Filter 2

(b)

Filter 3

(c)

Filter 4

(d)

Genetic algorithm optimisation

(a)

Brute force approach

(b)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

```

1 Function  $f$ :
2
3  $C1, B1, T1, C2, B2, T2, C3, B3, T3, C4, B4, T4 \leftarrow$  input; the values of
   central wavelength, bandwidth and type of filter of the four filters to
   be applied to the raw spectra
4
5  $X \leftarrow$  an empty set
6  $y \leftarrow$  the set of dry matter values of all the samples
7
8  $f1 \leftarrow$  getFilter( $C1, B1, T1$ )
9  $f2 \leftarrow$  getFilter( $C2, B2, T2$ )
10  $f3 \leftarrow$  getFilter( $C3, B3, T3$ )
11  $f4 \leftarrow$  getFilter( $C4, B4, T4$ )
12
13 for each spectrum from the raw spectra do
14    $x1 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, f1$ )
15    $x2 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, f2$ )
16    $x3 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, f3$ )
17    $x4 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, f4$ )
18
19   The set  $\{x1, x2, x3, x4\}$  is added to  $X$  as a new sample
20 end
21
22  $scores \leftarrow$  an empty set
23
24 for each  $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$  do
25    $regressor \leftarrow$  an  $\varepsilon$ -SVM is set up as regressor
26    $R^2 \leftarrow$  performCrossValidation( $regressor, X, y, folds = 5, seed = i$ )
27    $R^2$  is added to  $scores$ 
28 end
29
30  $fitness \leftarrow$  average( $scores$ )
31
32 return  $fitness$ 

```

Algorithm 1: Implementation of the fitness function f . The function “getFilters” receives three values for central wavelength, bandwidth and type of filter, and returns a filter with the given features; “applyFilter” receives a spectrum and a filter, and returns a scalar representing the filter response on that spectrum; “performCrossValidation” receives a regressor, the sets X and y , the number of folds for k -fold cross validation and the random number generator’s seed for fold partition, and returns the average R^2 result from the cross validation.

```

1 Function  $g$ :
2
3  $F1, F2, F3, F4 \leftarrow$  input; four COTS filters
4
5  $X \leftarrow$  an empty set
6  $y \leftarrow$  the set of dry matter values of all the samples
7
8 for each spectrum from the raw spectra do
9    $x1 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, F1$ )
10   $x2 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, F2$ )
11   $x3 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, F3$ )
12   $x4 \leftarrow$  applyFilter( $spectrum, F4$ )
13
14  The set  $\{x1, x2, x3, x4\}$  is added to  $X$  as a new sample
15 end
16
17  $scores \leftarrow$  an empty set
18
19 for each  $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$  do
20    $regressor \leftarrow$  an  $\epsilon$ -SVM is set up as regressor
21    $R^2 \leftarrow$  performCrossValidation( $regressor, X, y, folds = 5, seed = i$ )
22    $R^2$  is added to  $scores$ 
23 end
24
25  $fitness \leftarrow$  average( $scores$ )
26
27 return  $fitness$ 

```

Algorithm 2: Implementation of the fitness function g , that receive four commercial off-the-shelf filters. The function “applyFilter” receives a spectrum and a filter, and returns a scalar representing the filter response on that spectrum; “performCrossValidation” receives a regressor, the sets X and y , the number of folds for k -fold cross validation and the random number generator’s seed for fold partition, and returns the average R^2 result from the cross validation.